

EFFECT OF EMPLOYEES PERCEIVED ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT ON JOB SATISFACTION: EMPIRICAL EVIDENCE FROM COIMBATORE SME'S

Dr. M. Arunmozhi

Guest Faculty, Bharathiar School of Management and Entrepreneur Development,
Bharathiar University

Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

Corresponding Author Email: m.arunmozhi81@gmail.com

ABSTRACT--The primary goal of this study is to evaluate the influence of perceived organisational support on job satisfaction while accounting for organisational commitment's mediating function and organizational identification as moderating effect. This is a quantitative study that uses a convenience sample strategy to collect cross-sectional data from 250 employees of SME's in Coimbatore using an online questionnaire-based survey. This study found that organisational commitment mediates the relationship between perceived organisational support and work satisfaction using SEM in AMOS version 23. Perceived organisational support, on the other hand, has been found to be strongly connected to organisational commitment and job satisfaction. Furthermore, organisational commitment is favorably related to job satisfaction. This study was conducted at a single point in time and in a single city, Coimbatore, and hence has limited generalization of the results. This is the first study to combine the mediating variable of organisational commitment with the moderating variable of organizational identification in Coimbatore SME'. This study has important consequences for managers and policymakers. Managers and supervisors may improve employee satisfaction by adopting suitable rules about perceived organisational support and organisational commitment.

Keywords: Perceived Organizational Support, Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction, Organisational identification, SME's, Organizational Support Theory

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Ansari (2007), SME's are one of the most important and prominent sectors for the growth of the country's economy. Even in this day and age, this sector does not place enough emphasis on the value of human resources, despite the fact that they are in short supply (Saleem et al., 2012). Because the SME industry is very demanding, it demands enthusiastic and driven personnel who can work nonstop for long periods of time (Abdullah & Ramay, 2012). Once such employees are hired, it is the employers' job to maintain them by increasing their level of satisfaction (Baquer, 2010). Job satisfaction (JS) refers to an employee's upbeat attitude about various aspects of his or her job (Spector, 1997). The balance between the job's requirements and the individual's skills to meet those criteria results in JS (Dienhart & Gregoire, 1993). In the current situation, there is a need to emphasize the relevance of a match between an individual's talents and employment needs (Edwards, 1991). This is a key reason why policymakers must play a role in ensuring the application of various methods to achieve a balance and smooth the working sector's operating process (Oshagbemi, 2003).

Employees' levels of satisfaction in their company rise as a result of perceived organisational support (POS) (Webber et al., 2012). The more the organization's support for its employees, the greater the growth in employee satisfaction, demonstrating the direct relationship between these factors (Harris et al., 2007). POS is all about establishing or

creating a perception among workers that their employers will reward their hard work and will give full attention to their well-being (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Employee commitment rises as POS rises because workers get more engaged to their company and recognize that their efforts are not in vain (Colakoglu & Culha, 2010). It is a method that allows people to grasp their connection and mental compatibility with their organisation, and they think that their values are linked with those of their company (Garg & Dhar, 2014). It also leads to an increase in employee satisfaction (Gaun et al., 2014).

The study looks at the newly included model by using Organisational Identification as a moderating variable between organisational commitment and job satisfaction. Furthermore, it investigates OC as a moderating variable between POS and JS. This study intends to elucidate how the aforementioned variables interact with one another, especially in Coimbatore SME's. Based on the empirical data, certain particular policies might be developed with the SME's of Coimbatore in mind, which would be of great assistance to the authorities. Many different sorts of research on various industries have been undertaken in the past utilizing POS and JS. However, no study has been conducted, notably in the case of SMEs. As a result, this study addresses a research gap by concurrently presenting the mediating variable (OC) and the moderating variable (OI).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Perceived Organizational Support

Many scholars used organisational support theory (OST) to establish its function in the relationship between employees and organizations (Kurtessis et al., 2017). According to OST, an employee's level of satisfaction rises when his company is prepared to compensate him for his efforts and hard work (Eisenberger et al., 1986). It encourages employees to be more committed to their companies, and they work hard to ensure the success of their business. However, according to Bukhari and Kamal (2017), it is critical to demonstrate how firms can aid their workers by giving fringe benefits that help them in their everyday life, removing obstacles in their job, and inspiring them to do well. OST illustrates how much a firm cares for its employees' well-being by taking into account the interdependence of managers, employees, and directors. (Eisenberger and colleagues, 2001). It impacts an individual's intuition about whether or not the business is prepared to help its personnel when they are expected to do their responsibilities effectively and meet their standards (Wu & Liu, 2014).

Employees who receive greater organisational assistance are more productive and outperform those who do not receive any attention from their employer (Fulei et al., 2014). It aids in the development of stronger connections between employees and employers since both complement each other's needs, resulting in high profitability, excellent cooperation, increased employee spirit, and mutual support (Kunasegaran et al., 2016). POS primarily identifies the consequences and ramifications of organisational support on individual employees and businesses (Ghasemzadeh et al., 2017). According to Jeung et al., researchers also emphasized how an employee's performance in his organisation is impacted by what he wants and aspires to gain as a reward from his firm in the future, as well as what he earned in the past (2017).

Organizational Commitment

OC is explained as the stability of an individual's recognition with his specific organization (Wu & Liu, 2014). The commitment level arises when an individual's personality is appropriate under organizational requirements or when the aims of an organization are consolidated with individual objectives (McBey & Karakowsky, 2017). It is a procedure due to which people understand their connection and mental compatibility with their organizations, and they believe that their values are integrated with those of their firms (Gargr & Dhar, 2014). Employees who are more attached to their firm work hard with honesty to flourish their organization (Wu & Liu, 2014). Abuseif and Ayaad (2018) stated that OC is considered the most crucial factor that forces workers to fulfill the necessary needs of an organization and provides a competitive advantage over its competitors. Early

researchers illustrated that OC is the most extensively studied concept in organizational behavior literature (Yousef, 2002). Committed employees are considered to be more effective and profitable for their firms (Sharma, 2016).

OC is a mandatory element that shows a noticeable effect on any organizational performance. The absence of OC among employees can be hazardous for the firms (Naghneh et al., 2017). It motivates employees to unveil their full engagement and participation to complete their tasks without exerting pressure (Alipour & Monfared, 2015). If there is no commitment towards the organization, it would lead to a considerable increment in costs because of workers' high turnover ratio and hiring new employees (Zehra et al., 2017).

Job Satisfaction

Currihan (1999) defined JS as a combination of mental, physical, and environmental circumstances or a condition that causes a worker to communicate his job satisfaction. The balance between job requirements and an individual's ability to meet those needs results in JS (Dienhart & Gregoire, 1993). Employees who are experiencing JS's happiness are constantly eager to go to work because they believe that their enthusiasm will enable them to handle a large quantity of work (Ghasemzadeh et al., 2015). It is critical to understand JS since it has a favorable impact on employees' behavioral attitudes, such as a decrease in job stress and turnover intention, as well as an increase in OC and OI. (Pepe, 2010). JS is one of the most beneficial aspects that improve employees' health in both developing and developed nations (Kumari & Pandey, 2011). JS explains that it is a reaction of an individual to his job and his company (Waqas et al., 2014). JS is seen to be useful in enhancing employee performance since it causes people to become more relaxed, enthusiastic, and accountable for their responsibilities (Malhotra & Mukherjee, 2004). According to Locke (1969), JS is the sum of all the sentiments that employees have for their current employment, and the degree of JS can range from the highest satisfaction to the greatest discontent. It might be claimed that JS is a pleasurable psychological condition that results from a fair appraisal of workers' job performance, allowing them to achieve the organization's goals (Yang & Chang, 2008).

Organizational identification

Organizational identification is essential in the study of organisational behaviour because studies have discovered that workers' degrees of identification influence the organization's success (Ashforth & Mael, 1989). However, until the end of the 1980s, organisational identification was not well understood, and empirical investigations appeared to have confused it with other related variables like organisational commitment (Ashforth & Mael). Foote (1951), for example, defined

organisational identification as the adoption and commitment to a certain identity or sequence of identities. Foote also proposed that the fundamental basis for employees' motivation was identity. Only workers who associated with the organisation, according to the author, would be driven to act on behalf of the business by enhancing their job performance.

Brown (1969) proposed that organisational identification is a self-defining reaction to organisational engagement. Brown defines engagement in an organisation as a combination of four characteristics. The first aspect is the organization's attractiveness. That is, employees may find an organisation appealing if they believe their identity and the identity of the company are comparable (Bhattacharya & Sen, 2003; Bhattacharya, Sen, & Korschun, 2008). This aspect is connected to Kelman's (1958; 1961) view that beauty is a key precursor of organisational identification since, in general, people identify with organizations they find appealing. Brown (1969) identified the second issue as consistency of organisational and individual goals. This factor remained important in subsequent conceptualizations of organisational identification because authors such as Angle and Perry (1981) and O'Reilly and Chatman (1986) proposed that employees are said to be identified with an organisation when they accept and believe that their own values and goals are similar to those of the organisation.

Brown (1969) identified a third aspect as organisational loyalty. Loyalty is commonly regarded as a result of identification. Only workers who identify with the organisation have an emotional link with it, and that emotional bond influences their commitment to the

III. THEORY AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

The justifications of all the hypotheses are given below:

Impact of POS on JS

The increase in POS resulted in a rise in JS, indicating a positive relationship between the two variables (Shore & Wayne, 1993). An employee who enjoys doing work for his company would be more content with his employment if he believes his company will support him (Aselage & Eisenberger, 2003). Employee efficiency fluctuates with the degree of POS provided by their employers. The more POS they receive, the better their workers' ability to cope with specific organisational challenges, which tends to enhance their JS (Shanock & Eisenberger, 2006). When employees perceive that their company is ignoring them or that their boss is not supporting them, they feel unhappy. As a result, POS is positively associated to JS, which suggests that offering POS to employees leads to an increase in their JS level (Stamper & Johlke, 2003). Based on the logical reasons presented above, it is anticipated that:

company (Luchak, 2003). Brown's fourth and final identifying component is self-reference through organisational membership. This last component implies that an individual's affiliation with the organisation becomes evident at some point. In general, when individuals believe themselves to be members of a group, this perception is made explicit through the use of personal pronouns such as-we (Stets & Burke).

Despite the fact that Brown's (1969) model of organisational identification includes other aspects that he regarded to be part of the identification construct, academics continued to see it as one-dimensional. Furthermore, scholars proceeded to try to distinguish between organisational identification and a much related concept: organisational commitment. While there have been a large number of researches on organisational identification and organisational commitment, there is no consensus among scholars on the sequence in which they should be studied, nor on the distinctions and similarities between them. For example, Cheney and Tompkins (1987) claimed that identification and commitment are two distinct but related entities based on Cheney's (1983) identification work. They said that a person might identify with an organisation without committing to it. The writers used the example of a university professor who joins the institution's union because she or he agrees of their efforts but does not necessarily participate in those actions. The professor sympathizes with the union but is not dedicated to the union's goal. As a result, Cheney and Tompkins claimed that an employee might be identified with a company without being committed to it.

H1: *Perceived Organisational Support is related to Job Satisfaction positively and significantly.*

Impact of Perceived OS on OC

Employees become more responsible regarding their jobs due to POS because they think that they must have to pay back the favor of their organizations by doing their work effectively, which develops a sense of dedication among employees to perform their required tasks well. As a result, they become more committed to their organizations (Wayne *et al.*, 1997). Several researchers explained the nexus between POS and OC, which concluded that POS is an indispensable element to unveil the OC of employees, which means that higher POS tends to upsurge the level of OC rapidly (Riggle *et al.*, 2009). Therefore, workers become more devoted to their firms (Hackett *et al.*, 2001).

Social exchange theory explains that there arises a reciprocal relationship between two persons which means that when a person behaves well and manages another person effectively, the other person, in turn, feels the

responsibility to return this favor (Bateman & Organ, 1983). This social exchange theory is being implemented by many firms, which ensures favorable outcomes for both organization and workers because satisfying employee's requirements develop a significant sensation among them to be more committed to a firm (Gouldner, 1960). So, based on the above arguments, it is hypothesized that:

H2: *Perceived Organisational Support is associated with Organisational Commitment positively and significantly.*

Impact of OC on JS

Falkenburg and Schyns (2007) narrated that OC and JS are strongly associated with each other because when the employees are committed to their organizations, they become highly satisfied with their jobs. OC and JS are the most studied and analyzed variables in the Human Resource Management area as well as Organizational Behavior. OC leads to JS, but according to various studies, job satisfaction leads to OC, which means that reciprocated association exists between both variables (Lok & Crawford 1999; Yiing & Bin Ahmad, 2009).

JS is strongly influenced by the affiliation level of employees with their organization because when employees are ready to make any sacrifice for their firm, then their loyalty and attachment level creates peaceful feelings among them regarding job satisfaction (Moynihan & Pandey, 2007; Morrow, 2011). This relationship describes that OC emerges as an aggravation in JS because OC relates to an optimistic attitude of employees (Getahun *et al.*, 2008). When employees are engaged and identified with their organization, it results in a delightful psychological state that increases JS among employees (Porter *et al.*, 1974). So, based on the above arguments, it is proposed that:

H3: *Organizational Commitment is associated with Job Satisfaction positively and significantly.*

The Mediating Role of OC

According to Judeh (2012), OC partially mediates the connection between POS and JS. OC is one of the most significant components in research, which helps in studying different attitudes and behaviors of employees at work. Furthermore, it tells either worker is interested in taking part in the development or success of the organization or not (Ayers, 2010). It is already discussed that when organizations provide support to their employees and care about their well-being, then employees become satisfied with their jobs, but the level of job satisfaction among employees rapidly aggravates in the result of POS if there is a mediation effect of OC in between POS and JS (Wiener & Vardi, 1980).

OST, which is extracted from organizational exchange theory, also suggests that when the organization supports employees, they become more committed and satisfied with their job (Eisenberger *et al.*, 1986). It is also reported that jobs that enhance OC would also increase the prominent impact of organizational support perceived by employees on their JS, which means that OC would mediate the association between both variables. There is evidence that POS is related to JS positively by using OC as a mediating variable because OC produces an extreme association between both variables (Fuller *et al.*, 2003). According to past studies, OC arises from POS, and it is a predictor of JS (Meyer *et al.*, 2004). So, in the light of the literature mentioned above and supporting theory, it is hypothesized that:

H4: *Organizational Commitment mediates the association between perceived Organizational Support and Job Satisfaction.*

Organisational Identification's Moderating Role

Organisational Identification is the most valuable element which moderates the OC-JS relationship (Lawler & Hall, 1970). Based on researchers' unique studies, it can be claimed that a high level of OI helps employees to be absorbed in their work. Therefore they consider their job a central part of their existence (Hackett *et al.*, 2001). Employees become energetic regarding their jobs if they have a high level of organisational identification compared to those workers who feel tiredness and fatigue at their job, and it results in absenteeism due to low organizational identification level (Blau, 1986; Blau & Boal, 1987). Many researchers elaborated that the strength of OC-JS association is increased with the moderation of organizational identification (Tiwari & Singh, 2014). When employees get committed to their organization, they become more satisfied with their job, but if OI is the moderating variable between OC and JS, the connection between both variables becomes stronger and stable (Rotenberry & Moberg, 2007).

As per Chi *et al.* (2018), OC is positively related to JS even in that case, when OI influences their relationship strength being a moderating variable. It is examined by many studies if there is no moderation effect of OI, then JS still increases due to OC, but the lack of OI reduces the strength between interconnection of OC and JS (Mc Elroy *et al.*, 1999). Based on the above considerations, it is hypothesized that:

H5: *Organizational Identification moderates the association between Organizational Commitment and Job Satisfaction.*

Research Framework

The proposed model to investigate the five hypotheses is presented in Figure 1:

Figure 1: A Theoretical Framework

IV. METHODS

Participants and Procedure

This research was carried out at several SME's in Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India. Because all of the variables were completely defined and well-measured, this is quantitative research. Our research has a cross-sectional timeframe horizon and quasi study settings. The study's data were gathered from employees of various SMEs using the convenience sample approach. The employees of Coimbatore's SME's were the study's intended audience.

A questionnaire-based survey was used to collect the data. The questionnaires were delivered to 350 different workers from Coimbatore City's SMEs. There were 293 replies, for a response rate of 83.71 percent. A total of 250 questionnaires were selected for additional examination. Gender, age, qualification, employment experience, income level, and marital status were used to analyze respondents. The male gender made up 78 percent of the respondents in this survey. According to age, the bulk of responders (48 percent) were between the ages of 26 and 35. According to qualification, the majority of respondents, or 49 percent, held a Bachelor's degree. In terms of employment experience, the majority of respondents (54 percent) had 0-6 years of experience. According to income level, the majority of respondents earned between INR 15000 and 20000, accounting for 36%, while the majority of respondents were married, accounting for 58%.

Measures

The respondents were invited and asked to complete a questionnaire based on a five-point Likert scale with answers ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5).

POS: The 6-item scale created by Rhoades et al. (2001) was used to assess perceived OS, and the scale was found to be trustworthy with a Cronbach's Alpha score of 0.74.

OC: To assess organisational commitment, a 6-item scale developed by Mowday et al. (1979) was used, with a reliability value of 0.73.

JS was assessed using a 7-item scale devised by Brayfield and Rothe (1951). The scale's dependability was deemed adequate, with a Cronbach's Alpha rating of 0.71.

OI: This study used Ashforth & Mael, (1989) 5-item scale to evaluate organizational identification and reported a reliability value of 0.9, which was acceptable.

V. RESULTS OF THE STUDY

Data Analysis

Before doing the final analysis, this study used numerous tests to detect missing values, outliers, and the normality of the data. According to Sekaran's (2003) recommendations, all research must exclude replies with more than 15% missing values from data analysis. However, no missing values were found in this study, and the key reason for this was that data were obtained using an online questionnaire-based survey, where necessary fields made it mandatory for all respondents to complete the whole questionnaire. The data were further checked for outliers in accordance with Kline's (2005) guidelines. The Box Plot Matrix was used to identify two univariate outliers, and the Mahalanobis Distance test was used to investigate six multivariate outliers at $p < 0.001$; thus, eight outliers were excluded from the data, and 250 questionnaires were utilized for final analysis.

The Skewness and Kurtosis approach was used to verify data normality according to the guidelines provided by Byrne (2010). The data were regularly distributed using the Skewness and Kurtosis methods, with values of (1 and 3, respectively). Finally, multicollinearity was assessed using bivariate correlations according to the guidelines of Tabachnick and Fidell (2007), and all values were determined to be less than +0.85, ensuring that the data could be utilized for future analysis and that there was no multicollinearity concern. Harman's Single Factor Method was used to examine the data (Harman, 1967). This test was used to determine whether the majority of

the variation can be explained by a single component. When only one component was created, it explained 26.952 percent of the variation. It is less than the standard figure of 50%, as stated by Podsakoff et al. (2003), indicating that there is no common method variation in the data.

Descriptive Statistics, Reliability Analysis, and Correlation Analysis

Table 1 reveals that the mean values of all variables range from 4.09 to 4.36, indicating that the majority of respondents agreed on their replies. Standard deviation values smaller than one indicate that the proposed model

is a good match. According to Cronbach (1951); Nunnally and Bernstein (1994), all Cronbach's Alpha values should be larger than the criteria of 0.70 to demonstrate data reliability. Table 1's reliability analysis demonstrates that all of the values are more than 0.70. According to the correlation values, POS was positively connected with OC ($r = .681, p 0.01$), work satisfaction ($r = .518, p 0.01$), and job participation ($r = .461, p 0.01$). Similarly, organisational commitment was shown to be positively associated to both work satisfaction ($r = .498, p 0.01$) and job participation ($r = .411, p 0.01$). Job satisfaction was shown to be positively associated to job participation ($r = .508, p 0.01$). As a result, all of the correlation values are significant.

Table 1: Descriptive, Reliability and Correlation Analysis

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha	POS	OC	JS	OI
POS	4.09	0.38	0.79	1			
OC	4.24	0.80	0.81	0.681**	1		
JS	4.18	0.61	0.88	0.518**	0.498**	1	
OI	4.36	0.48	0.71	0.461**	0.411**	0.508**	1

Note: OC = Organizational commitment, POS = Perceived organizational support, OI = Organisational Identification, JS = Job satisfaction, ** $p < 0.01$

Structural Equation Modeling

There are two stages of SEM. The first stage relates to making a measurement model, and the second stage refers to making a structural model. First-order confirmatory factor analysis was applied since this study adapted questionnaires from past researches (Anderson, 1988). As coined by Hair *et al.* (2006) relating to the model fit, the researcher adjusted the model for modification indices and residual values. After applying the necessary

modifications and deleting the items having lower standardized regression weights, it was found that all the indices of the model were standardized, and the model was the fit one by following the criteria of Hu and Bentler (1999) and Hair *et al.* (2006). These model fit indices were CMIN=511.885, D.F. =199, CMIN/D. F. = 2.572, CFI=.87, NFI= .81, GFI=.84, AGFI= .80 and RMSEA=.079. Henceforth, the CFA model indicated an acceptable fit.

Table 2: Model Fit Indices of CFA after Modifications

Fit Indices	Standardized Values	CFA
CMIN	-	511.885
D.F.	-	199
CMIN/D.F.	≤ 5	2.572
GFI	$\geq .80$.84
AGFI	$\geq .80$.80
NFI	$\geq .80$.81
CFI	$\geq .80$.87
RMSEA	$\leq .08$.079

Factor Loading Values, Convergent and Discriminant Validity

As per Velicer and Fava (1998), the factor loading values in Social Sciences should range between 0.40 and 0.70. A factor loading value of at least 0.32 is regarded a good starting point (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2001). Here, all the factor loading values are more than 0.32 fulfilling the standard criteria for convergent validity. If the correlation value between two factors is less than ± 0.85 , then it can be referred to as the variables have discriminant validity; otherwise, there is a problem of convergence (Kenney,

2012). Henceforth, the data is fulfilling the standardized criteria for discriminant validity.

Structural Equation Model

In the second stage, the structural model was analyzed. The collected data fitted the suggested research model nicely since it showed the model fitness. While conducting SEM, results represented that CMIN= 331.048, D. F. =112, CMIN/D. F. = 2.956, CFI = .85, RMSEA= .08, NFI = .80, GFI=.87 and AGFI = .82. Henceforth, it was proved that the overall structural equation model is a good fit.

Table 3: Model Fit Indices for SEM

Fit Indices	Standardized Values	SEM
CMIN	-	331.048
D.F.	-	112
CMIN/D.F.	≤ 5	2.956
GFI	$\geq .80, \geq .85$.87
AGFI	$\geq .80$.82
NFI	$\geq .80, \geq .90$.80
CFI	$\geq .80, \geq .90$.85
RMSEA	$\leq .08$.08

Structural Equation Model

The factor loading values of a minimum of 0.32 are considered a golden rule of thumb (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2001). Here, all the factor loading values are greater than 0.32, depicting that the structural model is a good fit.

Hypothesis Testing

According to the standardized regression weights in Table 4, POS has an influence on JS ($\beta = 0.599$, $p < 0.001$), POS has an effect on OC ($\beta = 1.052$, $p < 0.001$), and OC has an effect on JS ($\beta = 0.344$, $p < 0.001$). H1, H2, and H3 of the study are now supported in this manner.

Table 4: Standardized Regression Weights

Paths	Estimates	S.E.	C.R.	P
POS \rightarrow JS	0.599	0.043	13.984	***
POS \rightarrow OC	1.052	0.087	12.023	***
OC \rightarrow JS	0.344	0.025	13.912	***

Mediation Analysis

AMOS version 21 was used for the mediation analysis. To analyze the mediation effects, we used a bootstrapping technique to examine the direct, indirect, and total impacts of the proposed model.

We employed Bollen and Stine Bootstraps with a bias-corrected confidence interval approach of 95 percent.

Table 5: Mediation Analysis

Hypothesis	Direct Beta without Mediation	Direct Beta with mediation	Indirect Beta	Mediation Type Observed
POS → OC → JS	0.488***	0.481***	0.312***	Partial Mediation

The beta values for direct effects (without mediator) are ($\beta = 0.488$, $p < 0.001$), direct effects (with mediator) are ($\beta = 0.481$, $p < 0.001$), and indirect effects (with mediator) are ($\beta = 0.312$, $p < 0.001$), all of which are significant. It represented a partial OC mediation between POS and JS. As a result, H4 of the study was supported.

Moderation Analysis

AMOS version 21 was used for the Moderation Analysis. There was no moderation since the interactional factor (OC x OI) was negligible ($p > 0.05$). As a result, H5 of the study was not supported.

Interaction Path for Moderation

Figure 4: Interaction Path for Moderation

VI. DISCUSSION

According to the findings of this study, POS was positively related with JS. When a company supports its employees by offering numerous amenities, their level of satisfaction rises. In other words, as the degree of employee happiness rises, so does the level of POS. Many other investigations, including Shore and Wayne (1993) and Aselage and Eisenberger (2003), found similar results. The relationship between POS and OC was shown to be positive and substantial, explaining why a high POS level tends to rapidly increase the amount of OC.

Employees become more connected or dedicated to their company when they get organisational support because they believe they must repay the organization's favour by executing their task with loyalty, as explained in the social exchange theory. Gouldner (1960), Wayne et al. (1997), and Allen et al. (2003) all investigated the positive association between POS and OC, and the current study is consistent with previous findings.

In terms of the data about the link between OC and work satisfaction, it appears that when OC increases, so does JS, demonstrating a positive and substantial relationship between these two variables. People's affiliation degree with their organisation has a great influence on JS because when employees are willing to make any sacrifice for their company, their loyalty and attachment level promotes calm sentiments toward JS. These findings are consistent with those of Lok and Crawford (1999), Getahun et al. (2008), and Morrow (2011), increasing the study's generalizability.

This study concludes that OC mediates the link between POS and JS to some extent. Employees become pleased with their jobs when companies support them and care about their well-being, but the level of JS among employees increases as a result of POS if there is a mediation effect of OC between POS and JS.

According to OST, employees become more dedicated to their company after receiving assistance from it, and they

are more pleased with their jobs as a result. Fuller et al. (2003) and Wiener and Vardi (1980) investigations both indicated the partly mediating impact of OC. The study also looked at the moderator impact of OI between OC and JS, and the results showed that OI did not play a role in moderating the relationship between OC and JS. In other words, OI neither strengthens nor weakens the OC-JS link.

VII. RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

Theoretically, this study is a unique addition to the current literature since it helps to unravel the relationship between POS and JS via the lens of OC. The study's findings may be used to learn more about the mechanism through which POS connects with OC and impacts employees' job satisfaction. POS is an essential component for revealing employees' commitment level, which means that a high POS level tends to swiftly increase the degree of OC.

Employees who are dedicated to their organisation have a joyful psychological state, which enhances JS among them (Riggle et al., 2009). This research also demonstrates how POS has a significant influence on employee work satisfaction. According to OST, an employee's demands may be readily met when his employer is willing to recompense his employee's efforts and hard work, resulting in an improvement in employee JS (Eisenberger et al., 2001).

In terms of practical applications, the findings require SME's to create adequate circumstances to increase employee happiness by concentrating on two most essential factors that fall under the tent of Industrial growth, namely POS and OC. Supervisors should investigate numerous elements and how these factors might be favorably applied to increase employee happiness. Managers should be aware of the working conditions that influence SME workers' commitment and satisfaction. Furthermore, supervisor training is required to increase supervisors' talents and skills in giving organisational assistance and building stronger connections with their subordinates.

VIII. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The present study also identifies certain limitations that future researchers should address in their research. Only SME's from Coimbatore city were studied, which limits its generalizability; thus, it must be used in other parts of India and throughout the world. Furthermore, while this approach has been explored solely in the SME sector, it must be used in other areas such as the health, education, and banking industries. In this investigation, data were collected at a specific moment in time. Data can be acquired at several points in time in the future. Furthermore, future researchers must incorporate more

moderators or mediators in the model. Finally, data were acquired using an online questionnaire-based survey (quantitative research), but future studies will need to collect data via interviews (qualitative research).

IX. CONCLUSION

The primary goal of this study was to investigate the relationship between POS and JS through the use of the mediating function of OC and the moderating impact of OI. To study the suggested model and analyze correlations among these variables, five hypotheses were created based on theories and existing literature. Using the convenience sample approach, data for this study were acquired through questionnaires distributed to workers of SME's. Several tests were performed on the acquired data, which met the standard standards and strengthened the usefulness of this research. Furthermore, studies for variable association were carried out using a two-stage SEM.

The findings revealed that POS was positively related to JS because when employees receive support from their organisation, their JS rises. Similarly, POS was positively connected with OC because workers become more engaged to their firm after obtaining assistance from it. However, the findings revealed that OC was both positively and substantially associated to JS. The first three assumptions were supported by these findings. Mediation analysis, on the other hand, revealed that OC partially mediates the link between POS and JS, hence confirming the fourth hypothesis. Furthermore, moderation analysis revealed that OI does not moderate the OC-JS association, implying that the fifth hypothesis was rejected. In summary, this research aids in understanding certain critical components of studying organisational management.

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